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WORKING-LIFE-INTEGRATED ENGINEERING STUDIES – SERVICE MARKETING PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Universities are keen on following the developments in working life as they find it important to keep education up to date and to support students' career development. Working life is under constant change and many of the working life requirements are industry specific. Organizations probably have several reasons for university co-

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operation. In this study we assume that 1) co-operation in education generates value for organizations and 2) this relationship can be regarded as service marketing. We utilize the concept of service marketing within the industry-education co-operation and present a case study of re-arrangements of engineering studies at one small European university.

Service marketing concept focuses on the whole process of marketing, not only on the marketing communication. The process concerns value creation and co-creation by service supplier and customer. A service is consumed at the same time it is produced and therefore, cannot be stored. Further, supplier provides recourses for customer's use, but the actual value emerges in customer's process of turning service into value.

The results of our discussions are in line with the concept of service marketing. Value to the industry partner is created in an interaction between that partner and a student. Students are thus evaluated on both the course completion and the value they produce for the client. This highlights also the role and importance of the commitment by the customer, i.e., the participating company. As a summary our results indicate that service marketing perspective is worth further investigation in university education development. We also propose a set of recommendations to utilize better the characteristics of service marketing in education.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Prologue

Working life is under constant change and many of the working life requirements are industry specific. This means that, for university educators, working life skills are a moving target. In this paper, we utilize the concept of service marketing into the industry-student cooperation and present a case study about analyzing experiences at one small European university.

Marketing is a widely used term and it has several definitions. The classical definition by Kotler [1] states: "Marketing is a societal process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating, offering, and exchanging products and services of value freely with others." This definition describes marketing as a process focusing on value creation within products and services, a notion which is important for this paper. Kotler also notes that according to the so called managerial definition by The American Marketing Association, marketing (management) is the process of planning and executing the conception, pricing, promotion, and distribution of ideas, goods, and services to create exchanges that satisfy individual and organizational goals. This definition brings the concept into the business world, but the most crucial notion for this study is that marketing is much wider concept than just marketing communication. It is a process producing value and it implies interaction between different parties.

This paper aims to open up discussion on the suitability of the concept of service marketing in consideration of university education, within the case of university-industry co-operation. In this layout, university courses are regarded as service products. However, the aim is not to discuss the philosophical foundation of university education or for example, the so-called third mission of universities any further. This paper introduces the results of our discussions that were stimulated by the congruence between our findings and the concept of service marketing. It should be noted that the course set up presented in this paper was designed before the introduction to the concept of marketing, the results were not guided to any direction with any conceptual framework.

1.2 Service marketing

Similarly as marketing, service marketing concept focuses on the whole process of marketing, not only on the marketing communication. The process concerns value creation and co-creation by a service supplier and a customer. In a few respects, services are clearly different from products. These features are often called as IHIP attributes [2]. The IHIP attributes are intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability of production and consumption, and perishability. Intangibility means that services are performances, they do not have a physical existence, and it is the most important factor differentiating services from products. Even though services can include some degree of tangible elements, the service process itself is an intangible performance. Heterogeneity has a dual meaning. Firstly, there is a great heterogeneity among service processes and service providers. Secondly, the service process in a company is found to be heterogeneous because of variation in its employees and in its customers, for example due to their needs and expectations. Perishability distinguishes services from goods in that they cannot be stored in inventories. Further, it is important to notice, that supplier provides recourses for customer's use, but the actual value emerges in customer's process of turning service into value.

It has been pointed out for example by Lovelock [3] that these characteristics exemplify the fact that services do not have a standard outcome, but the outcomes and their quality differ, depending on the specific customer and the service context. This notion has very important implications for our case, that is, treating university courses as service products for outside organizations. If we accept the above mentioned IHIP attributes concerning also university-industry co-operation in education, it would mean that very little of the value outcome to outside organisations can be achieved by pre-fabricating or by standardizing the courses. Value will be created during the co-operation and much by the student taking part in that process and by the organization in question. This seems to summarise the challenge in integrating education quality systems with the demands of teaching working life skills; that is, to standardise a moving target.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Case study

As Boeije [4] has mentioned, qualitative research is an applicable method for research, when a study has an explorative nature. The aim of this research is to explore the usefulness of the concept in understanding the phenomenon. Case studies typically use direct observation of the events being studied, as well as interviews of the people involved in the events, questionnaires and archived material [5]. Our study builds on an instrumental case study by Stake [6], where the case itself is not specific, but it provides an opportunity to create a new insight into issue, and offers a stepping stone for further research measures. A special state of affairs that is utilized in this study, is the development of teaching into the direction of benefits for companies.

The case presented here is a curriculum work model which offers the research methodology teaching long before starting the thesis and, on the other hand, prepares students to working-life together with the company already during studies. The whole is made up of basic studies in research methodology, laboratory work course in the corporate environment and subsequent thesis. The implementations are not separate courses, but support the thesis, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. As part of the curriculum work process that is integrated into working life, the thesis implementation model is used to support the advancement of both international and domestic students. The core of the process lies on three integrated courses.

The main part of the curriculum work is the laboratory work course, the scope of which is 2-30 credits according to the company-oriented project. Flexibility makes it possible to use the course in both bachelor's and master's stages. The course creates the capacity to solve the real problems identified by the companies with a research approach. At the same time, it provides the basis for longer-term business cooperation and allows the preparation and start of the thesis. The course will be carried out as a project that is planned together with the company, the student and

the supervisor from the university. A project plan, follow-up reports and a final report are prepared for the project, reflecting the implementation of a student's plan.

2.2 Interviews

This paper builds on the interviews of teachers and discussions among the teachers and our research group. In the following we present the main results of the interviews.

In this consideration we intentionally focused on teachers. Students are also the main players in the whole setting, but they do not have insight into the changed situation, as they have no actual possibilities to compare their experiences with those of previous year students. We present interviews of three university lecturers, who were actively planning and piloting this new curriculum work model. The interview is based on four questions, and the main part of the replies are presented here (as direct translations to English).

Question 1.

What did you do and what was the change compared to before?

“The most important thing is the implementation and introduction of a chain of three courses in a company-oriented way. First, the research methodology creates the capacity for a research approach in future interaction between the student and the company. Secondly, the Laboratory Work Course / Individual project work course connects the student and the company to the target company for a long time (up to 20 cr) and lays the groundwork for the thesis and "introduces" the student and the company to each other. Here you learn general project work models and also get to know the target company's project practices and, for example, information systems. The company can “assess” whether the student should be recruited for them, but there are still no salary costs. The scope of the project (2-20 cr) can also be agreed with the company. Third, a supervised and scheduled thesis process helps to solve a company problem in a high-quality and company-oriented manner.”

Question 2.

What did the changes mean for the teaching work and the teacher?

“When planning the content of teaching and arranging student meetings, the special features of the respective business contact have had (have been) taken into account. To some extent, the company-oriented examples have been confidential and have not been used other than in the supervision of an individual thesis. On the other hand, a company-driven “right problem” also challenges the teacher to sharpen his or her own guidance and address the specifics of the company.”

“In the long run, I believe that this will accumulate knowledge capital for teachers, and on the other hand, the company will get a solution to the current problem as well as, if desired, from the author of the thesis who is able to solve the problem to the expert himself. To some extent, the supervised thesis process requires more time from the teacher to meet with the student, on the other hand, from the university's point of view, the completion of theses on time is easier. It is also important for the company to get the results of the thesis as planned, usually as part of a larger project.”

“The biggest change is the move away from comprehensive structured teaching and project guidance to a more creative model that includes more degrees of freedom and shifts responsibility more towards the student. The transition from teaching to coaching and support requires a particular mental effort; there is also an element that allows projects to fail when not all the threads can be held in the hands of the teacher. Confidence in students is further sharpened as a whole, as well as acceptance of the idea that not everything learned may be easily or unambiguously measured or even at least fully perceived during the project. A key starting point is to build working life and entrepreneurial skills as one of the starting points for lifelong learning.”

Question 3

What have the students liked about the whole?

“To some extent, the workload of students has increased, but on the other hand, the guided processes distribute the work more evenly over the entire study period. In the big picture, students like the fact that there are more frequent contacts with the supervising teacher and they get feedback about their own work all the time. Company orientation in the topics of projects and theses (including bachelor's theses) is a motivating factor. Supervising teachers have found the new model useful.”

“The students have generally been satisfied with the supervised thesis writing process, the positive feedback came from the fact that teacher meetings have been arranged during the course, so these were felt to be quite useful. There were things to note about the course schedule, especially the placement of the lectures on the calendar. Some had begun to move forward with their work faster than the course schedule was, and thus the lectures were no longer considered useful at that point.”

Question 4

What have companies liked about the whole? What have they stated about the results, and in particular about the results brought by this new model?

“Companies actively participate as mentors in courses and are interested in students' ideas. Mentoring can be seen, for example, in GoFIRM virtual company operations (an operational tool in the course set). There are constantly more topics for project work and theses coming from companies. Companies often have hopes of ensuring confidentiality issues. Companies often emphasize getting results on schedule, but unfortunately there is not always a “required” completion of a degree on schedule. This still requires clarification on both sides so that the benefits for all parties become clear.”

“In the big picture, companies consider the opportunity offered to “take a longer trip” together with the student before possible recruitment or starting a thesis to be good.”

“So we moved from trenches of separate courses to working together. Important factors were the feedback received from companies on the skills perceived by graduates and the graduates' own perceptions of the skills needed in working life and the operating models implemented there.”

3 DISCUSSION AND PROPOSITIONS

We started this study from and with an assumption that 1) co-operation in education generates value for organizations and 2) this relationship can be regarded as service marketing. Our findings of the above mentioned course setting are in line with the concept of service marketing. The interviews imply that the value to the industry partner is created in an interaction between that partner and a student. Despite students' increased independence the industry partners are keen on having a relatively sustaining co-creation relation with the students. Industry partners clearly have their own goals and timelines. Even teachers have a clear role there, the main outcome is derived from industry partner – student interaction.

There are some evidence, that this re-arrangement of above-mentioned courses did produce more value to the industry partners. Direct measurement is not possible as each project is content and context specific, and the processes of student – organisation co-operation variate. This is also in line with the basic premises of services marketing. Our case did not bring out any evidence that this development would be harmful to education or to its scientific level. On the contrary, it had a positive influence on students' motivation, which in many generated more positive outcomes.

It also seems that students value the possibility to interact closely and for a longer time with industry partners, even if they were evaluated on both the course completion and the value they produced for that client. Further, we noticed that the longer time a company partner and student co-operated, the more value was created. This meant also that student's ability to create value was noticed and

her/his changes to be employed evidently got better. This highlights also the role and importance of the commitment by the customer, i.e., the participating company.

Further, following the earlier, the vast body of research on service marketing and managerial literature on the issue may offer tools and concepts to the development of university education in regard to industry co-operation. Therefore, we propose that service marketing is an important perspective in developing university education and definitely worth further investigation. The literature on service marketing suggest that a service is a process that is produced and consumed simultaneously and the value of the service to the customer is generated in the customer's processes. In educational setting this means that the student is assessed other than through the course substance and the related reports or other written assignments. The student is assessed through the effectiveness of his or her collaboration with the organization and the value it provides to the company. The value to be produced for the customer organization is not necessarily the same as the criteria for assessing the substance content of the course. Based on these findings, we make the following suggestions to support the student:

- *Organizing more and longer-term cooperation with the organization.* Both the student and the organization get to know each other, and the opportunities to generate value together improve.
- *Highlighting the procedural nature of the cooperation with organizations during the courses.* As an example, the student is introduced to the principles of process consulting (see for example Schein [7])
- *Highlighting the marketing nature of the cooperation,* for example by including a brief introduction to marketing and sales in the course content (Notice: this need derives from the actual co-operation process, not as a worldview, ideological or other decision).
- *Planning and highlighting the productisation and modularization of the co-operation process for both the student and the organization.* Both of these contribute to value creation, and knowing the process speeds up familiarization and finding a common course of action. However, the student is not an employee of the company, so it is not exactly the same introduction process that applies to the company's own employees. Even the processes of the customer organization are company specific the familiarisation to the basic features of service marketing process may help the student to work with the customer organization.

Our findings led us into an important consideration: If we do accept the IHIP attributes of services (mentioned earlier in the text) concern also university-industry co-operation in education, it would mean that value to the outside organisation would derive from student – organisation co-operation. This would mean that taking these principles into account could make it possible to improve students' chances of being

useful to companies and thereby improve their chances of finding employment after their studies. Even we do not have a rigorous research setting backing up our notions we were surprised at how well these principles explained the findings made in the context of this course setting and also in the past. Based on our findings we suggest that concept of services marketing is definitely worth further investigation.

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